

Cs₂AgBiBr₆ Perovskites: Designing Stable, Sensitive and Selective Eco-friendly Ozone Sensors

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Lead halide perovskites have shown great promise for gas sensing applications due to their ability to detect and respond to gas exposures at room temperature. However, the toxicity of lead raises concerns, hindering their widespread use. To address this limitation, this study explores the potential of the lead (Pb)-free Cs₂AgBiBr₆ perovskite as a sensing element for room-temperature gas detection. This eco-friendly sensor, synthesized at room temperature without the use of harmful organic solvents, operates at low voltage (0.1 V) minimizing energy consumption. The perovskite material is synthesized using a precipitation method under ambient conditions, ensuring a cost-effective and environmentally friendly fabrication process. The influence of morphology on ozone (O₃) sensing performance is investigated, revealing that the microsheets exhibit the highest sensitivity. The sensor also demonstrates remarkable stability over time and under various humidity and temperature conditions, ensuring its reliable and robust performance in diverse environments. Notably, the sensor exhibits exceptional selectivity to O₃ over other gases, including nitric oxide (NO), hydrogen (H₂), methane (CH₄), and carbon dioxide (CO₂). This selectivity, along with the interaction between the gases and the perovskite surface, is confirmed through both experimental measurements and first-principles calculations. This technology holds immense potential for applications in air quality monitoring and industrial safety.

1. Introduction

The problem of indoor and outdoor air quality has become more critical in a world characterized by rapid industrialization and urbanization.^[1,2] The increase in air pollution levels, caused by emissions of toxic gases and volatile organic compounds (VOCs), represents a significant risk to public health and the environment.^[3] Consequently, various gas sensors have been employed for the identification of these hazardous substances, facilitating the real-time monitoring and protection of both human health and environmental well-being.^[4,5] The versatility of gas-sensing technologies stems from the development of materials that selectively interact with specific target gases. Among these sensing elements, metal oxide semiconductors are the most prevalent due to their fast response and remarkable sensitivity to harmful gases.^[6] However, such materials often require lengthy synthesis processes and high operating temperatures, which can potentially compromise their long-term stability and increase energy consumption.^[7]

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The emergence of lead (Pb)-halide perovskites is considered noteworthy in the field of efficient gas-sensing elements. These materials are well-known for their unique optoelectronic properties, enabling applications such as LEDs and photovoltaics.^[8,9] Moreover, they possess features such as sensitive surfaces, abundant active sites, and controllable defect density, which facilitate the selective detection of gaseous compounds at room temperature.^[10–12] Several Pb-halide perovskite materials, including both organic–inorganic and all-inorganic, have been employed for the detection of various gases such as molecular oxygen (O₂), ozone (O₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and ammonia (NH₃), exhibiting exceptional sensitivity and response.^[13–17] Nevertheless, despite their outstanding sensing performance, concerns regarding the toxicity of Pb hinder their commercial exploitation, as even low concentrations of Pb can have severe implications for both human health and the environment.^[18,19] Pb exposure is associated with various health issues, including neurological and cardiovascular problems in humans, while environmental Pb exposure can result in soil and water contamination, harming ecosystems and wildlife.^[20,21]

In response to these concerns, the scientific community has shifted its focus to designing environmentally friendly, Pb-free metal halide perovskites. These perovskites are obtained by the substitution of Pb²⁺ ions with alternative non-toxic divalent metals such as Sn²⁺, or with isoelectronic trivalent elements, like Bi³⁺ for enhanced stability.^[22] Meanwhile, the well-known double perovskites are derived from the incorporation of a monovalent and a trivalent metallic element.^[23] An obvious choice toward this end would be to combine trivalent Bi with a monovalent noble metal, such as Ag. Although research on the synthesis and optical properties of these materials has expanded, reports on the detection of gaseous compounds using such materials are very limited, focusing only on the detection of NO₂, NH₃, and NO.^[24–28]

Despite the great potential of Pb-free metal halide perovskites in detecting both reducing and oxidizing gases, to the best of our knowledge, there have been no reports of their capability to detect O₃ gas. O₃ is a highly oxidizing agent and is widely used in various applications such as water purification, food processing, and medical sterilization.^[29–31] However, when O₃ levels exceed permissible limits, it can pose significant health risks, including respiratory problems and cardiovascular diseases. This damage is primarily caused by the formation of reactive oxygen species, which can damage cells and tissues in the human body.^[32] Therefore, there is a pressing need for inexpensive O₃ sensors with exceptional sensitivity to support air-quality monitoring and at the same time be compatible with Internet of Things (IoT) devices.

The present study contributes to the gas sensing technology by introducing environmentally friendly perovskites that are efficient, stable under harsh conditions, and cost-effective due to their quick room-temperature synthesis. Specifically, ligand-free Cs₂AgBiBr₆ double perovskites in the form of microsheets, faceted microflowers, and spherical microflowers were synthesized using a precipitation method under ambient conditions. This study further elaborates on the optimal morphology and size for accurate detection and selectivity for various gases, combining experimental data with atomistic simulations to identify specific adsorption sites and surface interactions. The sensing

performance, particularly under O₃ exposure, and the stability at high temperatures and relative humidity levels are demonstrated. The microsheet-based perovskite sensor was distinguished for its full reversibility and selectivity toward O₃ among the NO, H₂, CO₂, and CH₄ gases. This selectivity is further validated by atomistic simulations, which confirm the experimental observations and provide insights into the active sites on the perovskite surface and the underlying sensing mechanisms of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ double perovskites against all the tested gases.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Optimal Features of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ Perovskites for O₃ Detection

Microparticles of the double perovskite Cs₂AgBiBr₆, free of capping ligands and exhibiting diverse morphologies and sizes, were synthesized to assess their reactivity toward O₃ and determine the optimal characteristics for gas sensing applications. Within the scope of this work, three discrete morphologies of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ – sheets, spherical and faceted flower-like particles – were successfully synthesized.

The ligand-free microsheets (Figure 1a), with dimensions of 22.8 ± 6.2 μm, were obtained from the precipitate following a protocol that involved the introduction of the inorganic precursors dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) into ethanol. Currently, the spherical microflowers (Figure 1b), with an average size of 0.90 ± 0.29 μm, were collected from the supernatant of the same mixture. Faceted flower-like microcrystals, sized 2.14 ± 1.29 μm (Figure 1c), emerged upon drop-casting the precursor solution onto a substrate at 80 °C. Similar flower-like particles were synthesized by Greul et al. through high-temperature synthesis, and their formation was attributed to the rapid solvent evaporation, which accelerated the crystallization process and resulted in the formation of agglomerates.^[33] The first two morphologies were each deposited on interdigitated commercial Pt-electrodes (G-IDEPT5, Metrohm with a gap and width of 5 μm) each for O₃ sensing evaluation, while the third was directly grown on the electrodes.

Compositional analysis using Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) confirmed the presence of Cs, Ag, Bi, and Br in all synthesized morphologies (Figure S2, Supporting Information). Their crystal structures were determined via X-ray diffraction (XRD), revealing that all morphologies were crystalline in the cubic Cs₂AgBiBr₆ structure with space group Fm $\bar{3}$ m (ICDD 01-084-8699) (Figure S3a, Supporting Information). Notably, additional minor reflections at ≈30.9° and 44.3° were also detected and attributed to the unreacted precursor AgBr and the secondary phase Cs₃Bi₂Br₉, corroborating findings from prior studies on the synthesis of the same material.^[33]

The gas-sensing performance of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ perovskites with three distinct morphologies was evaluated under standard laboratory conditions (room temperature and ambient light; Figure 1d–f). A voltage range of 0.1–1 V was applied, with the specific voltage depending on the morphology, and a constant pressure of 600 mbar was maintained within the gas-sensing chamber. The two larger morphologies (microsheets and faceted microflowers) exhibited effective gas-sensing responses at a minimal voltage of 0.1 V. However, this voltage was insufficient to

Figure 1. FESEM images and size distribution diagrams (insets) of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ perovskite-based sensors with microparticles of a) sheet-, b) spherical flower- and c) faceted flower-shaped morphology. d–f) Electrical response of perovskite-based sensors under different O_3 concentrations, at room temperature. Normalized oxidation curves as a function of time (insets in d, e).

activate the smallest morphology, spherical microflowers, likely due to their comparatively wider bandgap (Figure S3b–f, Supporting Information). Tauc plot analysis revealed a bandgap energy of 2.30 eV for the spherical microflowers, 2.05 eV for the microsheets, and 2.22 eV for the faceted microflowers. Consequently, a constant voltage of 1 V was applied to the spherical microflowers during gas-sensing measurements. The observed variation in absorbance spectra can be attributed to the interplay between microparticle morphology and size. Larger structures, such as sheets and faceted flowers, displayed a consistent absorbance plateau below 450 nm (Figure S3c,e, Supporting Information). In contrast, the spherical microflowers, composed of smaller entities, exhibited a distinct absorbance peak ≈ 435 nm (Figure S3d, Supporting Information). This observation is consistent with previous studies on $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$, where single crystals demonstrated the characteristic plateau,^[34] while smaller nanostructures ≈ 10 nm exhibit a peak.^[35] The ability of the larger particles to operate efficiently at a low voltage (0.1 V) offers a significant power advantage. This operational efficiency, combined with the room-temperature operation and absence of external stimuli (heat or UV irradiation), minimizes energy consumption, making these materials promising for portable and cost-effective sensing devices.

Upon exposure to O_3 , all examined morphologies of the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ material exhibited a p-type behavior (Figure 1d–f). This behavior was evidenced by an increase in current intensity upon exposure to O_3 until reaching saturation point, and a decrease in current intensity when exposed to synthetic air. This behavior was consistently observed across all tested O_3 concentrations, ranging from 2300 to 4.3 ppb. The consistent p-type behavior suggests that the interaction of O_3 with the perovskite sur-

face leads to an increase in hole concentration, which is responsible for the observed increase in current. Notably, the microsheets-based sensor demonstrated the ability to differentiate between low O_3 concentrations.

The normalized oxidation curves (insets in Figure 1d,e) provide a clear representation of the sensor's response to different O_3 concentrations. Normalizing the current to the maximum value for each O_3 concentration allows for a direct comparison of the sensor sensitivity across a wide concentration range. This analysis is crucial for evaluating the sensor's ability to distinguish low O_3 levels, which is essential for air quality monitoring and human health protection. These curves also revealed distinct differences in the sensing performance of the different $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ morphologies. The normalized oxidation curves highlighted the sensor's ability to detect O_3 levels as low as approximately 160 ppb (Figure 1d, inset, dark blue curve), which is well below the 300 ppb OSHA's PEL-STEL limit (Permissible exposure limit – Short-term exposure limit).^[36] Conversely, the other samples exhibited poor responses unable to discern different O_3 concentrations, suggesting that both faceted and spherical microflower-based sensors were not suitable for O_3 detection, especially at low concentrations (Figure 1e–f). Therefore, the microsheets morphology was identified as the most effective for O_3 detection, demonstrating high sensitivity even at lower concentrations. The difference in the sensing behavior between the microcrystals could be attributed possibly to several factors, including variations in total surface, surface termination, and defect density. The larger porous surface area of the microsheets morphology may enhance sensitivity by providing more active sites for O_3 adsorption and introducing defects that affect charge transport and gas adsorption (Figure S4, Supporting Information). Additionally, the differ-

Figure 2. a) Calculated response and b) Response/recovery times of the sensor as a function of O₃ concentration.

ent preferential growth orientations observed in the XRD patterns (Figure S3a, Supporting Information), suggest variations in surface termination, which can influence the interaction with O₃ molecules. This finding was also contrasted with a report on analogous CuO morphologies by Luo et al., where flower-like configurations showed enhanced responses to volatile gases compared to their sheet-like counterparts.^[37] This difference may be originated from variations in porosity, surface, defect density, or even defect type.^[38–43]

2.2. Response to O₃ and Stability to Time, Humidity, and Temperature of the Microsheet-Based Sensor

2.2.1. Sensor's Performance

The sensor's response, calculated from the $I_{\text{gas}}/I_{\text{air}}$ ratio (where I_{gas} and I_{air} denoted the maximum and minimum current values, respectively, during oxidation), exhibited a distinct correlation with O₃ concentration, increasing from ≈ 1.07 at 168 ppb to 1.38 at 2300 ppb (Figure 2a). Notably, the response could be fitted into two distinct linear regions. At concentrations lower than ≈ 750 ppb, the response demonstrated an increased rate, as indicated by the larger slope of the curve (blue fitting curve, Figure 2a). Conversely, at higher concentrations, the response displayed a

slower rate of increase (green fitting curve, Figure 2a). A similar transition from a high to a low response rate was reported in prior studies.^[44,45] Sun et al. observed this phenomenon in multi-walled carbon nanotubes upon exposure to O₃,^[44] while Cui et al. reported a similar occurrence in 2D phosphorene nanosheets when subjected to NO₂.^[45] In the former case, the shift in response trend was attributed to the saturation of the perovskite surface with O₃ molecules while in the latter, it was linked to the decrease in the mobility of charge carriers due to scattering effects from gas molecules adhering to the sensor's surface.

Achieving a rapid response, fast gas detection, and quick recovery times is essential for a high-quality sensor. The temporal metrics for response (t_{res}) and recovery (t_{rec}) times in relation to O₃ concentration are critical parameters. These are determined by analyzing the exponential growth and decay characteristics of the sensor's electrical response across a range of gas concentrations.^[46] It is noteworthy that the microsheet-based sensor demonstrated a rapid response, with response times of less than 30 s for elevated gas concentrations and under 50 s for lower concentrations (Figure 2b, black points). Furthermore, the sensor's recovery process was markedly efficient, with durations of less than 2 min (Figure 2b, blue points). At the detection threshold of 168 ppb, the sensor is capable of recovering in than 83 s.

Upon detailed comparison with leading sensors operating at room temperature, primarily those utilizing metal oxides synthesized through high-temperature or lengthy processes, the microsheet-based sensor's performance is comparable to certain devices at similar O₃ concentrations (Figure 3a, orange frame, Table S1, Supporting Information). These sensors include AgIn₂O₃ (1wt%),^[47] NiAl,^[48] and Au@TiO₂,^[49] which operate within the O₃ concentration range of 100 to 500 ppb without requiring external stimuli. However, some sensors, such as ZnO-SnO₂^[50] and In₂O₃,^[51] require irradiation to function effectively. Conversely, our sensor exhibits a reduced response compared to others, such as ZnO,^[52] InGaZnO (IGZO),^[53] ZnO-gold,^[52] 0.1% Au TiO₂-WO₃,^[54] and TiO₂-In₂O₃.^[55] The operation of these sensing elements is triggered by an external stimulus, such as UV or LED irradiation, leading to increased cost and higher power consumption. Notably, carbon nanotubes, a different type of sensing element from metal oxides, exhibited a similar response pattern without external triggering, even when tested at significantly higher O₃ levels (5000 ppb).^[44]

Promising results have emerged regarding the performance of the Cs₂AgBiBr₆ microsheet-based sensor compared to other metal halide perovskites utilized for O₃ detection at room temperature without requiring external triggering (Figure 3b, Table S2, Supporting Information). While the response of Pb-free perovskite-based sensor may not be the highest among all the metal halide perovskite-based sensors at comparable O₃ concentrations (180 ppb), its response time is notably the shortest, and its recovery time ranks among the quickest. Despite not having the highest response, this cost-effective, environmentally and health-friendly alternative can efficiently detect low gas concentrations in seconds without the need for any external light source. This underscores the potential of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ microcrystals, which could be further optimized, akin to their well-established counterparts in the field.

Figure 3. Comparative performance of the microsheet-based sensor. a) Response of the microsheet-based sensor to O₃, in comparison with other semiconducting sensing elements reported in the literature.^[44,47–56] The comparison is made at each sensor's detection limit, noting the operating temperature and any requirement for light irradiation. Materials with performance characteristics similar to the sensor in this work are highlighted by the orange circle. - b) Response at 180 ppb of O₃ and the respective response/recovery times in relation to metal halide perovskites previously reported in the literature.^[17,46,57] Response and recovery times are indicated by open and filled symbols, respectively. The morphology of each material is also illustrated, with the Cs₂AgBiBr₆ microsheets from this work highlighted in green.

2.2.2. Short- and Long-Term Stability

The short-term repeatability and long-term stability of the sensors constitute critical parameters for ensuring its reliability and accuracy over time. Each sensing cycle exhibited a consistent pattern characterized by a current increase in the presence of the oxidizing gas, followed by a full recovery in the presence of synthetic air, indicating the strong reversibility of the sensor (Figure 4a). The absence of drift, even after three successive cycles, further suggests that the sensor can be utilized for continuous air monitoring. In addition, the long-term stability of the sensor was evaluated after six weeks, showing similar sensing

behavior, reinforcing the sensor's reliability, (Figure 4b) while both morphological and structural characteristics remained unaltered at the end of the sensing process over time (Figure S5a,b, Supporting Information). The chemical stability of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ micro-sheets before and after O₃ exposure was investigated by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Particularly, narrow scans were conducted for all the relevant elements of interest, including Cs 3d, Ag 3d, Bi 4f, and Br 3d core levels, however, no chemical shifts were observed, suggesting that the chemical environment remained unaffected by the O₃ treatment (Figure S6, Supporting Information). This could be because the sensing mechanism relies on electronic effects or interactions at specific, possibly dilute active sites. These interactions might not translate into broad changes in the core-level binding energies of the bulk elements, or any subtle changes might be beyond the detection limits of XPS.

2.2.3. Stability Against Humidity

In various real-world applications that involve semiconductor gas sensors, including air-quality monitoring and agricultural sensing systems, the effect of humidity on sensor performance remains a critical consideration. To probe the effect of humidity, the stability of the microsheet-based sensor was evaluated under the influence of controlled relative humidity (RH%) levels at room temperature under different O₃ concentrations ranging from 2890 down to 168 ppb (Figure 4c). The gas sensing tests were conducted under both dry conditions and at controlled at RH levels from 30% to 70%. The results showed similar electrical current diagrams across all humidity conditions, demonstrating the sensor's ability to detect O₃ effectively in such conditions. Notably, the sensor's responsiveness improved significantly with increasing RH, especially at lower O₃ levels, where the response rate increased by more than tenfold (Figure 4d), while it retained its morphological features (Figure S5e, Supporting Information). This behavior stands in contrast to most chemiresistive gas sensors whose response typically deteriorates at high humidity levels,^[17,58] making the microsheet-based sensor even more noteworthy.

A plausible explanation for the enhanced gas sensing behavior upon humidity could be assigned to the adsorption of water molecules on the surface of the perovskite material. Similar to Cs₂SnCl₆, Cs₂TeCl₆, and Cs₂AgBiBr₆ perovskites previously studied as effective humidity sensors, the adsorption of water molecules on the surface of these materials likely enhances the sensor's conductivity.^[59–61] In particular, the adsorption of humidity involves both chemisorption and physisorption, occurring at low and high humidity levels, respectively. At low humidity conditions, H₂O molecules are chemically adsorbed onto the perovskite surface, releasing a proton (H⁺). The H⁺ is then transferred to an adjacent water molecule, forming H₃O⁺. Subsequently, the proton undergoes a series of transfers from site to site, which leads to an increase in the sensor's conductivity. Conversely, a high humidity environment, water molecules form multiple physisorbed layers on perovskite's surface, creating a liquid-like network of hydrogen-bonded water molecule layers. The hydration of H₃O⁺ is energetically favored in the presence of liquid water, resulting in proton transfer described by

Figure 4. a) Short-term stability diagram of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ micro-sheets upon three successive cycles. b) Long-term stability diagram of the as prepared and after six weeks upon exposure to different O_3 concentrations. c) Electrical response over time without and with relative humidity in the range of 30% to 70% under different O_3 concentrations. d) Calculated response as a function of concentration for different relative humidity levels. e) Temperature dependence of the electrical response at 2000 ppb O_3 exposure. f) Temperature-dependent XRD pattern.

the equation $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ = \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}$. The hydrated proton then moves between adjacent H_2O molecules within a continuous layer of water, contributing further to the increase of conductivity.^[62]

The effect of humidity on the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ perovskite structure at the end of the sensing process was investigated by XRD (Figure S5c,d, Supporting Information). The analysis revealed a slight shift of $\approx 0.02^\circ$ in the characteristic peaks of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ toward higher angles compared to the initial pattern. This shift indicates a compressive strain,^[63] possibly arising from the humidity-induced formation of crystallographic defects. Additionally, the appearance of a distinct diffraction peak at $\approx 32.3^\circ$ is likely attributed to the presence of a tetragonal BiOBr crystal phase, suggesting a partial decomposition of the material into BiBr_3 , followed by its hydrolysis into BiOBr .^[64,65]

2.2.4. Stability Against Temperature

To further investigate the stability of the sensor under harsh conditions, the effect of working temperature was evaluated. Experiments were conducted at variable temperatures while the sensor was exposed to O_3 at a concentration of 2000 ppb (Figure 4e). Interestingly, the sensor was able to operate even at elevated temperatures, suggesting its stability and potential for use in environments with fluctuating or high temperatures. However, it was noticed that by increasing the temperature, the electrical current decreases from $\approx 0.25 \mu\text{A}$ down to $0.05 \mu\text{A}$ (Figure 4e). This phenomenon could be explained by the competition between thermal adsorption and desorption of atmospheric oxygen on the perovskite surface. A similar explanation was proposed by Bejaoui et al. for the CuO O_3 sensor.^[66] That study suggested that

Figure 5. Electrical response of the microsheet-based sensor when detecting a) NO and c) H₂ under different gas concentrations, at room temperature. Calculated response as a function of b) NO and d) H₂ concentration. The insets in (a,c) show the normalized oxidation curves of NO and H₂, respectively, as a function of time. e) Radar chart showing the normalized response $(I_{\text{gas}}/I_{\text{air}})/C_{\text{gas}}$ of the sensor in the different gases.

at room temperature, the conduction process was dominated by low resistance due to the high density of holes. However, when the temperature was increased, the desorption increased, leading to a smaller hole accumulation layer and consequently to the increase of the resistance.

Furthermore, to elucidate any alterations induced by the thermal process to the perovskite material, which could potentially explain the observed sensing curves, temperature-dependent XRD analysis was performed (Figure 4f). Intriguingly, no new diffraction peaks emerged under high-temperatures; however, significant peak shifts toward lower angles were noted. These shifts indicated the lattice expansion of the Cs₂AgBiBr₆ at elevated temperatures (100 and 200 °C), suggesting a modification in lattice parameters that could potentially account for the differences in conductivity. Upon cooling to room temperature, the diffraction peaks reverted to their original positions, implying that these structural changes were reversible. Additionally, to assess the synergistic effect of O₃ together with the temperature on the material, XRD patterns were acquired at the conclusion of the sensing process following exposure to O₃ (Figure S7, Supporting Information). These patterns remained unaffected, confirming that the crystal structure was preserved at the end of the sensing process, with side phase intensities diminishing at 200 °C, consistent with the known effect of annealing at 250 °C for the complete conversion of the precursors into the desired Cs₂AgBiBr₆.^[33]

2.3. Response and Selectivity in Various Gases

To ascertain the selectivity of the Cs₂AgBiBr₆ microsheet-based sensor toward O₃ gas, additional tests were conducted with both reducing and oxidizing gases were conducted, including nitric

oxide (NO), hydrogen (H₂), methane (CH₄), and carbon dioxide (CO₂) (Figures 5 and S8, Supporting Information). Similar to its response to O₃, the sensor exhibited p-type sensing behavior in the presence of NO, however, to prevent the formation of NO₂, pure N₂ was employed as a recovery gas (Figure 5a). Remarkably, when exposed to NO, the sensor could resolve gas concentrations as low as 2 ppm (Figure S9a, Supporting Information), with excellent stability even after multiple sensing cycles (Figure 5a inset). However, the sensor's response to Cs₂AgBiBr₆ microsheets was modest, even at 10 ppm (Figure 5b). Moreover, in contrast to O₃ response, which exhibits a steeper slope at lower concentrations and a more gradual increase at higher concentrations, the NO response shows a smaller slope initially and a more pronounced increase at higher concentrations. This behavior could indicate that gas molecules might need to reach a certain concentration threshold before significantly affecting the sensor.

Unlike O₃ and NO, H₂ is not considered toxic; however, at concentrations above 40,000 ppm (in air), it poses a high explosion risk.^[67] Despite its reducing nature, H₂ elicited a current response similar to that observed for NO, suggesting a distinct sensing mechanism. While Cs₂AgBiBr₆ demonstrated remarkable repeatability upon exposure to O₃ and NO exposure, its response to H₂ exhibited significant baseline drift, indicating a possibly irreversible sensing process. This suggests that the sensor is best suited for single-use or limited-use H₂ detection. This drift could be potentially attributed to H₂ molecules diffusing into the perovskite crystal lattice, possibly inducing changes in the material.^[46] Studies suggest that hydrogen atoms preferentially adsorb onto the interstitial sites of the Cs₂AgBiBr₆ lattice, creating new bonding states.^[68] Although the sensor could detect H₂ at levels as low as 20 ppm, its overall response was poor, even at higher concentrations.

In order to examine the effect of H_2 on $Cs_2AgBiBr_6$ microsheets at the end of the H_2 sensing process, XPS was employed. Narrow scans of Cs 3d, Ag 3d, Bi 4f, and Br 3d of the microsheets before and after H_2 exposure showed, similarly to O_3 , no chemical shift, indicating the absence of chemical interactions on the surface of the material (Figure S10a–d, Supporting Information), while the survey XPS spectra showed no alterations as well (Figure S10e, Supporting Information). The crystal structure upon H_2 exposure was also evaluated by the means of XRD. This analysis revealed a noticeable increase in the (311) peak intensity (Figure S10f, Supporting Information) and a slight increase in the intensity of byproduct peaks, suggesting that structural modifications and partial decomposition of the perovskite occurred upon H_2 exposure.

Finally, in the context of reducing gases, CO_2 and CH_4 were also tested for cross-sensitivity (Figure S8, Supporting Information). Contrary to H_2 , both sensors exhibited an n-type sensing behavior, as expected, with poor current changes under high gas concentrations, indicating low charge transfer between the perovskite material and the CO_2 and CH_4 gases at room temperature.

Considering the observed variations in current corresponding to the concentrations of each target gas, a radar chart delineating the normalized response versus gas concentration was constructed to evaluate the selectivity of the developed sensor (Figure 5e). The graphical representation definitely demonstrated the sensor's pronounced selectivity toward O_3 , surpassing its sensitivity to other tested gases. Notably, NO and H_2 caused moderate responses, while CO_2 and CH_4 exhibited minimal sensor response.

2.4. DFT Calculations to Predict $Cs_2AgBiBr_6$ Gas Sensor Selectivity

To shed light on the response trend to the different tested gases, first-principles calculations were employed to investigate the adsorption interactions between the $Cs_2AgBiBr_6$ surface and O_3 , NO, H_2 , CO_2 , and CH_4 target molecules. Since an ideal sensor material is characterized by its ability to form robust bonds with the target gas while inducing significant alterations in its electronic structure upon adsorption, investigation of the binding strength of the target molecules to the perovskite surface as well as of the density of states (DOS) through Density Functional Theory (DFT) simulations serves as a promising avenue to elucidate the experimental observations. However, finding a suitable surface model to accurately simulate the experimental conditions and provide meaningful insights is challenging due to several reasons. Perovskite surfaces can exhibit structural complexities such as different terminations, defects, and reconstructions, which pose difficulties in selecting the most relevant to the experiment surface model. Introducing defects or dopants into the surface model adds another layer of complexity, as does determining the energetically favorable configuration of the adsorbate molecules on the non-ideal surface. In addition, balancing computational feasibility with the need for an accurate representation of the surface properties further complicates the selection, as the size of the simulation cell needs to be large enough to capture the essential surface properties while remaining small enough

Figure 6. Adsorption energies in the strongest binding site for O_3 , NO, H_2 , and H target species, on the TB surface without defects (green) and on the defected TB with V_{Br} (Br-Bi) surface (magenta). (i) The strongest binding sites of each target species (O_3 , NO, H_2 , and H, respectively) on the TB surface without defects and (ii) on the defected TB surface with V_{Br} (Br-Bi). Cs, Ag, Bi, Br, O, N, and H atoms are illustrated as cyan, silver, purple, brown, red, blue, and white spheres, respectively.

to allow for an extensive investigation of the configurational space.

Herein, the (100) oriented surfaces based on the bulk cubic crystal structure of $Cs_2AgBiBr_6$, as synthesized by A. H. Slavney et al., were selected.^[1] Taking into consideration insights from prior theoretical investigations,^[70,71] these surfaces were modeled as seven-layer slabs of alternating $BiAgBr_4$ and Cs_2Br_2 layers. Two possible terminations exist for these models; termination A (TA: $BiBr/AgBr_3$) and termination B (TB: $CsBr$), both illustrated in Figure S11 (Supporting Information) along with the different adsorption site types for each one. Prior theoretical research by G. Volonakis and F. Giustino demonstrated that under various synthetic conditions, $CsBr$ -terminated (TB) surfaces are favored in $Cs_2AgBiBr_6$ perovskites.^[70] However, our sensor material may comprise a combination of both terminations, highlighting the importance of examining both cases to assess the experimental sensing trends. For both TA and TB ideal (i.e., non-defected) surfaces, extensive research was conducted to identify the energetically preferable adsorption site for each target molecule, with overall results shown in Figures 6 and S12 (Supporting Information). Notably, O_3 showed the strongest interaction (-0.7 eV) regardless of the termination, whereas NO exhibited a strikingly different behavior with respect to the termination of the surface; while approaching the TA surface yielded an energetically favorable conformation of -0.17 eV, the TB surface showed almost no interaction with NO (0.01 eV). The experimentally observed significant response of the sensor to NO gas cannot be simply extracted from adsorption energy alone and is very likely due to some long-range effect that is inaccessible by DFT calculations,

or the presence of defects on the surface. Vacancies, interstitials, and dopants are among the common defects in these materials. Such defects may have significant implications on the material's properties and performance, affecting its electronic behavior. In fact, the stable chemical potential range for pristine (i.e., defect-free) $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ is quite narrow, as demonstrated in the theoretical study of Z. Xiao et al.^[72] Amongst others, Bi vacancies and AgBi antisites are deep acceptors and the dominant defects under Br-rich conditions, Ag vacancies are shallow acceptors and can easily form, and Br vacancies are identified as intrinsic donors. Since Br vacancies (V_{Br}) can be found in both the TA and TB uppermost layer of our surface model,^[73] the role of this type of defect on the performance of the developed sensor was selected to be further investigated.

Focusing on the CsBr-terminated surfaces (TB), two different sites for Br atoms exist, thus two different types of Br vacancies; Br atoms that bond to Bi atoms (Br-Bi) and Br atoms that bond to Ag atoms (Br-Ag). According to P. Chen et al.,^[71] Br atoms are more easily removed from (Br-Bi) sites, due to lower formation energy. Following this result, 1 Br (Br-Bi) atom was removed from the uppermost layer of the TB surface. The effect of the V_{Br} (Br-Bi) on the adsorption energies and configurations of the target molecules compared to the defect-free case is illustrated in Figure 6. The results of the V_{Br} (Br-Ag) sites of TB surfaces are presented for comparison in Figure S12 (Supporting Information). In the most astonishing cases of O_3 and NO, once a V_{Br} (Br-Bi) is introduced to the perovskite surface, O_3 enters the vacancy site, adopting a bidentate conformation and resulting in a more than four times stronger interaction (-3.23 eV) compared to the defect-free surface. At the same site type, the NO molecule showed an even more remarkable hundredfold enhancement (-1.26 eV) compared to the non-interacting defect-free surface.

Additionally, in the presence of H_2 , the interaction between molecular hydrogen and the perovskite surface is minimal, with nearly negligible binding energy (≈ 0.1 eV) across various non-defected and defected surface scenarios, as indicated in Figures 6 and Figure S13 (Supporting Information). However, while H_2 molecules do not exhibit strong interaction with the perovskite surface, dissociation of H_2 into two hydrogen atoms (H^*) occurs readily on the defected surface (TB surface with V_{Br} (Br-Bi)), releasing 0.8 eV of energy. This dissociation process is not favorable in ideal, non-defected surfaces, suggesting the presence of vacancies in the experimentally synthesized sensor.

The interaction strength was also enhanced in the cases of CO_2 and CH_4 (Figure S12, Supporting Information). For CO_2 the interaction almost doubled and the molecule adopted a bended configuration within the vacancy site. This behavior suggests a chemical bond-like interaction, which breaks at least one of the double bonds in CO_2 , also consistent with P. Chen et al.^[71], a fact that can further rationalize the formation of localized mid-gap states upon the CO_2 - V_{Br} (Br-Bi) interaction (Figure S15c, Supporting Information, see below). On the other hand, for CH_4 there was still no indication of significant interaction, neither from the binding energy values (Figure S12, Supporting Information) nor from the electronic compensation of the defect sites (Figure S15d, Supporting Information, see below). It should be noted that binding energies higher than ≈ 0.3 eV do not suggest good selectivity, as N_2 is found to bind with -0.27 eV on defected TB surfaces with V_{Br} (Br-Bi) (Figure S14, Supporting Information).

To elucidate the underlying electronic structure changes upon adsorption of the target gases, the Partial Density of States (PDOS) was calculated at the global minimum conformation for each gas case (Figures 7 and S15, Supporting Information). In the PDOS of the ideal, defect-free surface without adsorbed gas (Figure 7a), the valence band (VB) and conduction band (CB) are located at ≈ -0.5 and -1.0 eV, respectively, with their orbital contributions consistent with those of bulk $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ as calculated by E.T. McClure et al.^[74] Once a Br atom that is connected to a Bi atom is removed from the uppermost layer of the surface, i.e., when a V_{Br} (Br-Bi) is introduced to the surface, both CB and VB are shifted to lower energy values, and new states from the Br and Bi atoms emerge near the Fermi level, narrowing the electronic gap (Figure 7b), a result aligned with the findings of P. Chen et al.^[71] These defect-induced states vanish upon the adsorption of strongly interacting gases like O_3 , NO, and H, which fill the V_{Br} site (Figure 7c,d,f), while persisting in the case of the weakly interacting H_2 molecule (Figure 7e). Noteworthy, O_3 and H adsorption (Figure 7c,f), is accompanied by an observed “healing” effect and opening of the gap, with H returning the PDOS profile to a non-defected state, as most hydrogen states are located deeper in the VB. In the case of O_3 , new states from the oxygen atoms emerge at the VB, with a prominent peak at the valence band maximum (VBM). A different effect is observed when NO molecules occupy the vacancy sites as new distinct states appear around the Fermi level, originating primarily from the N and O atoms (likely due to the radical nature of the NO molecule, with the unpaired electrons generating localized mid-gap states) with secondary contributions from the Bi and Br atoms (Figure 7d).

A complementary perspective into the electronic structure changes upon gas adsorption is provided also in Figure S15 (Supporting Information), where the charge density difference plots for all target molecules with the TB-defected V_{Br} (Br-Bi) surface are presented, showing significant charge transfer from the uppermost surface atoms to the strongly adsorbed species.

3. Conclusion

This research marks the first use of Pb-free, environmentally friendly $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ double perovskites for O_3 detection down to a few hundred ppb without requiring external stimuli such as heating or irradiation. Furthermore, it investigates the O_3 sensing capabilities of three distinct, ligand-free shapes –microsheets, spherical microflowers and faceted microflowers– revealing that the choice of shape significantly influences the gas sensing properties. Among the synthesized morphologies, the microsheet-based sensor proved to be the most effective morphology for O_3 detection, capable of resolving concentrations down to 168 ppb under a very low power (0.1 V), with a response time of less than 40 s. This performance surpasses that of traditional, toxic lead-based perovskites used for room-temperature O_3 detection and is comparable to most state-of-the-art materials operating under similar conditions. Additionally, the microsheets displayed good reversibility over repetitive gas sensing cycles and remarkable long-term-stability. Unlike most chemiresistive metal oxide-based sensors, the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ microsheets were capable of operating even under harsh conditions, including high relative humidity levels and elevated temperatures.

Figure 7. Partial density of states (PDOS) of the (100) oriented TB $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ model surfaces a) without defects and b) defected with V_{Br} (Br-Bi). PDOS of the defected with V_{Br} (Br-Bi) TB surface upon adsorption of c) O_3 , d) NO, e) H_2 , and f) H. The Fermi level is set to zero eV.

Moreover, the cross-sensitivity of the microsheet-based sensor toward other gases, including NO, H_2 , CO_2 , and CH_4 , demonstrates an excellent selectivity of the perovskite sensor for O_3 while also showing great potential for detecting NO and H_2 . However, it proves unsuitable for detecting CO_2 and CH_4 due to insufficient signal generation. Theoretical insights evaluating the relative trends of adsorption energies for the target gases, along with the emerging characteristics in the DOS profile upon their adsorption, further highlighted the crucial role of surface defects in the sensing process, with Br vacancies identified as the most effective active sites for O_3 detection.

Overall, this work contributes to the development of room-temperature, low-power, and environmentally friendly gas sens-

ing devices, expanding the understanding of lead-free metal halide perovskites for gas detection. The combination of experimental and computational approaches provides valuable insights into the active sites and sensing mechanisms of metal halide perovskites, paving the way for further research and applications in air quality monitoring.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: Chemicals: The chemical precursors CsBr (99.999% trace metal basis), AgBr (99.9%- Ag), and BiBr_3 (99.999%, anhydrous, metals basis) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Strem Chemicals, and Thermo Fisher Scientific, respectively, and used without further treatment

before the synthesis of metal halide perovskites. The solvents, Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO, $\geq 99.9\%$, anhydrous) and ethanol ($\geq 99.8\%$, absolute) were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich and Fisher Scientific, respectively.

Syntheses of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ Microflowers and Microsheets: The precursor solution was prepared by dissolving 0.5 mmol of CsBr powder, 0.25 mmol of AgBr powder, and 0.25 mmol of BiBr_3 in 10 mL of DMSO under ambient conditions. The ligand-free $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ microsheets were synthesized through a room-temperature precipitation approach. Specifically, 1 mL of the precursor solution was introduced into 10 mL of ethanol, resulting in the mixture's color to instantly turning yellow, indicative of rapid crystal nucleation and growth. After a 20-min precipitation period, the precipitate was collected, deposited onto electrodes for sensing measurements, and subsequently dried under vacuum. Concurrently, the supernatant contained spherical microflowers, which were also deposited onto electrodes and dried under vacuum.

In contrast, the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ faceted microflowers were grown directly on electrodes upon heating. A few μL of the precursor solution were deposited on preheated electrodes at 80°C (heating plate temperature set point) and maintained at this temperature for 20 min to facilitate growth.

Morphological, Structural, and Chemical Characterization of Microcrystals: Field-Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM, JEOL JSM IT700HR) working at 20 kV was employed to analyze the surface morphology of the perovskites. Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDS, Dry SD60 detector) was utilized for the elemental analysis of the prepared samples. The crystal structures were investigated by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD, Bruker AXS D8 Advance copper anode diffractometer) over the 2θ collection range of 10° to 50° with a scan rate of $0.02^\circ/\text{s}$, using a monochromatic $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation source ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$). Temperature-dependent XRD measurements were performed over the same 2θ range to study the structural evolution of the material under varying thermal conditions. The samples were subjected to controlled heating at room-temperature, 100° and 200°C . The absorbance spectra of all fabricated materials were measured by UV-Visible spectroscopy (Perkin Elmer Lambda 950 UV/Vis/NIR) in the range of 380 to 650 nm. The chemical compositions and electronic states of the perovskites were determined by X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS, SPECS-Germany, FlexMod) equipped with a PHOIBOS 100 1D-DLD energy analyzer and an Al $\text{K}\alpha$ monochromatic X-Ray source (1486.7 eV) operated with 200 W and 15 kV. The spectra that were recorded were the following: survey spectra, C 1s, Cs 3d, Ag 3d, Bi 3d, Br 4d, and O 1s. The survey and the high-resolution spectra were recorded at a pass energy of 30 eV. All the binding energies in XPS spectra were calibrated using the C 1s at 284.8 eV as a reference. The data analysis was performed with SpecsLab Prodigy and CasaXPS (Casa software Ltd, DEMO version). A Tougaard baseline was used in combination with a Gaussian-Lorentzian function for the high-resolution spectra deconvolution, which was executed by Origin-Pro 2016 software.

Gas-Sensing Measurements and Analysis: The gas-sensing measurements were conducted at room temperature, in a custom-made gas-sensing chamber, providing a controlled environment for the electrical assessment of the perovskite-based sensors. The gas sensing setup consisted of gas suppliers connected with mass flow controllers, coupled with a stainless-steel chamber which was initially evacuated down to 10^{-3} mbar (Figure S1, Supporting Information). To evaluate the O_3 sensing capability of all fabricated materials, a commercial O_3 analyzer (Thermo Electron Corporation, Model 49i) was employed. The analyzer was used to supply and record accurately controlled O_3 concentrations that were introduced in the chamber at a flow rate of 500 sccm (standard cm^3/min) flow. Electrical current measurements over time were executed using an electrometer (Keithley 6517A) by applying a constant voltage. The values of the voltage ranged from 0.1 V for the microsheets and faceted micro-flowers to 1 V for the spherical microflowers. The sensing process was initiated by exposing the sensors to O_3 gas for 150 s, followed by a 200 s recovery with synthetic air. All samples were exposed to different O_3 concentrations ranging from 2300 ppb down to 4 ppb. During the experimental procedure, the pressure in the chamber maintained constant to 600 mbar.

The impact of temperature, combined with O_3 gas, was investigated by replacing the custom chamber with a commercially available Ceramic Heater Type Micro Probe System (MPS-CH, MVPS III-PTTC, NEXTRON),

capable to operate within the range of room temperature up to 450°C . The influence of relative humidity (RH) was also studied by connecting the MPS-CH with a humidity controller. Humidity was provided by injecting deionized (DI) water in the humidifier and the levels of 30, 45, 50, and 70% of RH were studied.

The performance of the sensors for each gas was assessed through their response (R), defined as:

$$R = \frac{I_{\text{gas}}}{I_{\text{air}}} \quad (1)$$

or

$$R = \frac{I_{\text{air}}}{I_{\text{gas}}} \quad (2)$$

where I_{gas} and I_{air} are the electrical current values after saturation in the presence of reducing/oxidizing gas and synthetic air, respectively. Response and recovery times are determined using the equations:

$$I = \begin{cases} I_0 + A_d + A_g \left(e^{-\frac{t-t_c}{t_{\text{res}}}} - e^{-\frac{t}{t_{\text{res}}}} \right), & I \leq I_0 \\ I_0 + A_d e^{-\frac{t-t_c}{t_{\text{rec}}}}, & I > I_0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where t_{res} and t_{rec} are the response and recovery times respectively, I_0 is the initial current value, A_d and A_g are the decay and growth amplitudes respectively and t_c is the time where the current reaches its maximum value.

Computational Methodology: Seven-layer slab models were employed to simulate the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ surfaces, in accordance with previous studies.^[70,71] These (100) oriented slabs were constructed from the bulk cubic phase of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$, with lattice constants $a = 36.8848 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 11.2499 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 11.2499 \text{ \AA}$ (finite in the x-direction with a vacuum gap of 20 \AA , and periodic along the y- and z-directions).^[69] Specifically, symmetric slabs consisted of 3 (4) Cs_2Br_2 and 4 (3) BiAgBr_4 alternating layers were constructed for termination A (termination B).

Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations were conducted using the Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP).^[75,76] The Perdew–Becke–Erzenhof (PBE) parametrization within the Generalized Gradient Approximation (GGA) was employed for the exchange-correlation (XC) functional.^[77] The projector augmented wave (PAW) formalism was utilized to model interactions between valence electrons and ions.^[78] A plane wave energy cut-off of 400 eV and van der Waals interactions treated with the DFT-D3 scheme of Grimme were considered.^[79] Convergence criteria included an energy cut-off of 10^{-6} eV for electronic degrees of freedom and a maximum force threshold of $0.01 \text{ eV}\cdot\text{\AA}^{-1}$ for relaxation of atomic positions. Brillouin zone integration was performed using a $1\times 4\times 4$ Γ -centered k-point mesh, with Gaussian smearing of 0.1 eV. A denser $2\times 5\times 5$ Γ -centered k-point mesh was used for the PDOS calculations. During structure optimization, the cell volume and shape remained fixed, while atoms in the top three surface layers and the adsorbates were allowed to relax.

The adsorption energies ΔE_{ads} were calculated as $\Delta E_{\text{ads}} = E_{(\text{X}+\text{slab})} - E_{\text{slab}} - E_{\text{X}}$, where $E_{(\text{X}+\text{slab})}$ is the energy of the slab with the adsorbed X molecule (with X being O_3 , NO, H_2 , CO_2 , CH_4), E_{slab} is the energy of the slab, and E_{X} is the energy of the X molecule in vacuum. For the case of NO, the open-shell (spin-polarized) configuration was used.

Charge density difference plots were generated using VESTA software^[80] on a $0.001 \text{ (e/bohr}^3)$ isosurface, calculated as the difference of the electron density between the slab + X complex system and the sum of the isolated components within the conformation of the complex.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

DFT, double perovskites, environmentally friendly materials, gas sensors, ligand-free metal halides, microflowers perovskites, microsheets perovskites

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